

**LIFE AND ILLNESS ARE PROBLEMS THAT ARE THE FOCUS OF
ATTENTION OF RELATED PROFESSIONS**

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Nobel Prize Laureate (2004) in Chemistry Aharon Chekhanover is an Israeli biologist, foreign member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, professor at the Faculty of Bioengineering and Bioinformatics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. M.V. Lomonosov, expressing his opinion on personalized medicine, said that "Now we are on the verge of a new revolution - the transition to personalized medicine, when the forecast is approaching 100% accuracy, and the effectiveness of treatment is growing by orders of magnitude. Obviously, the future of medicine will be based on our knowledge of the structure of DNA, on the ability to decipher it." "In the future, we will be able to intervene in the damaged genome and fix mutations. This is one of the main "features" of the future medicine - that the doctor will work with healthy people more often than with sick people, a sick person will become a rarity, like some exotic animal now" [12]. The main tasks of the PPPM include:

- 1) Identification of signs of the disease at the stage of preclinical pathology, with the identification of targets adequate for pharmacological prevention;
- 2) Pharmacocorrection in order to suppress the pathological process at the preclinical stage.

Preclinical diagnostics to solve these problems should:

1. Be able to timely determine the genetic predisposition to the occurrence of a specific pathology.
2. With high reliability, determine the quantitative indicator of the occurrence of pathology at its preclinical stage.
3. Monitor the dynamics of biomarkers and biopredictors, thereby monitoring the responses of individuals at risk to pharmacological preventive measures.
4. The existing model of interaction between the attending physician and the patient will be supplemented by the model of the medical adviser - a healthy person.
5. Approximate calculations show that with such observation and timely adoption of measures to eliminate existing shifts, life expectancy will increase by 8-15 years.

One of the key points for the successful implementation of NCD prevention programs is the development of targeted, well-organized and evidence-based prevention of NCDs in children and adolescents. We are firmly convinced that it is from childhood, after carrying out "genetic exploration" and selecting the appropriate contingent of children with hereditary risk factors, that it is necessary to begin the prevention of chronic NCDs.

In recent years, there has been a rapid development of technologies for reading the structure of the genome or exome, as well as determining the functional state of genes. Currently, more than 30 clinical and epidemiological projects using the genome or exome sequencing method have already been registered in the world, which allows us to hope for a significant increase in the possibilities of personalizing predictive medicine based on the results of cohort genetic and epigenetic studies. Even more impressive are the predictive data on the development of new technologies, which will not only allow early diagnosis and predict their development, but also significantly prolong human life.

A system of individual prevention approaches based on a genetic passport will be developed, tested and implemented to create the foundations for preventive personalized medicine. An individual genetic passport should allow the identification of molecular genetic risk markers for non-communicable diseases, rare mutations that cause monogenic diseases (familial hypercholesterolemia, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, hemochromatosis, cystic fibrosis, etc.) and silent mutations in autosomal recessive inheritance. At the same time, it becomes possible to detect mutations in the genes responsible for the metabolism of drugs (pharmacogenetics) and molecular genetic markers of the risk of non-communicable diseases that are characteristic of individual populations (population genetics).

Great hopes are associated with proteomics, the development of proteomic technologies that will allow for the assessment of the risks of occurrence and early diagnosis of socially significant and professionally caused diseases, using the results of the analysis of the molecular composition of biological material. Based on biomarkers, analytical systems that use biobar coding to determine individual disease risks. It is planned to create experimental samples of test systems that allow reading, comparative analysis and comparison of molecular barcodes in normal and pathological conditions.

A special place is occupied by the opportunity to create a new technology for preclinical diagnosis of body dysfunctions based on the identification of markers

of endoplasmic reticulum stress. Which will allow for preclinical diagnosis of various pathological conditions [13].

In our everyday life, generally accepted factors continue to be used and improved, which are used both in planning the prevention of non-communicable diseases and in maintaining a high quality of life and longevity. Such factors are: motor activity, rational nutrition, observance of the daily routine and hygiene of rest, work that brings satisfaction, the presence of a life goal, normal sleep, household hygiene, the ability to manage emotions and maintain optimism, a happy marriage, giving up bad habits, hardening, etc. There is a firm understanding that in order to maintain health, you need to choose the appropriate lifestyle, while considering that genetics “loads the gun”, but it is the environment that “pulls the trigger”. At the same time, one should not forget the well-known principles of preventive medicine, widely used in practice, the long experience of which has confirmed its effectiveness. These include:

- comprehensive and differentiated approach,
- continuity of preventive measures,
- Increasing the level of sanitary culture through the promotion of modern knowledge and methods of medical prevention

